

Rice mutants and their mother cultivars differed in yield potential (see table). IR6, IR8, Bas 370, Jajai 77, Sada Gulab, Sonahri Sugdasi, Pokkali, Lateefy, and DR82 yielded more straw and grain than their mutants. N and P were higher in the parents than in the mutants; K content was variable.

The higher N and P content in parent genotypes contributed to increased yield. ■

Developing a functional model of rice panicle growth

R. Sadasivam, C. Kailasam, R. Chandrababu, A. Arjunan, M. Nagarajan, and S. R. Sree Rangasamy, *Crop Physiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India*

We grew short-duration rice cultivars ASD 16 and CO 41 under field conditions using a randomized complete block design with 12 replications during 1988 wet season. The pattern of panicle growth on 60 panicles/plot that emerged on the same day was studied from emergence to maturity. Five panicles per plot were removed 12 times to 30 d after emergence and dry weight recorded.

Panicle development followed a sigmoidal pattern (see figure). Two distinct lag phases, one at the beginning and one at the end of panicle growth, were evident. These two lag phases were separated by rapid linear growth between 3 and 21 d after emergence. We tried

Panicle growth in rice cultivars, Coimbatore, India, 1988 wet season.

several growth equations: Richard's function, logistic function, nonlinear function, and negative exponential function.

Type of function	Functional form	R^2 value	
		ASD16	CO 41
Richard's function	$W_t = (1 + e^{b-kt})^{-1/n}$	0.960	0.945
Logistic function	$W_t = (1 + e^{b-kt})^{-1}$	0.863	0.810
Nonlinear function	$W_t = (a+bt)^{-1}$	0.780	0.693
Negative exponential function	$W_t = ae^{-bt}$	0.632	0.542

Richard's function gave the best fit to describe panicle growth in short-duration

rice cultivars. The Richard's equations of panicle growth follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ASD16 } W_t &= 295(1 + e^{1.188 - 0.242t})^{-1.852} \quad (R^2 = 0.960) \\ \text{CO41 } W_t &= 1.79(1 + e^{1.259 - 0.228t})^{-2.0} \quad (R^2 = 0.945) \end{aligned}$$

ASD16 had a mean relative growth rate (\bar{R}) of 157 mg/panicle per day, compared with 151 mg in CO 41.

Mean relative growth rate was calculated as

$$\bar{R} = \frac{K}{(n+1)}$$

(Suggested by D R Causton and J C Venus [1981])

The biochemistry of plant growth. Edward Arnold, London. p. 92.) ■

Herbage potential of rice cultivars

T. Kupkanchanakul, B. S. Vergara, and F. T. Parao, *Agronomy, Physiology, and Agroecology Division, IRRI*

Rice herbage can be an important animal feedstuff: it has high nutritive value, it is readily available in most ruminant production areas, and rice grain yield is not sacrificed by herbage removal. We studied the herbage potential of 20 deepwater and 4 lowland rice cultivars under irrigation at IRRI in the 1989 wet season.

The experimental field was plowed twice. Fertilizer was incorporated basally at 60-40-40 kg NPK/ha 1 d before transplanting. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing with two seedlings/hill. Herbage was cut at the collar level of the last fully developed leaf 40 d after transplanting (DT) and from different plots at 60 DT. Treatments were repeated three times.

Differences in growth and herbage yield were observed at 40 and 60 DT (Table 1). There was a positive relationship between herbage yield at 40 and 60 DT ($R = 0.595^{**}$). Deepwater cultivars Khao Mali, Pan Tawng, Khao Lod

Chong, and Khao Praguad gave high herbage yields, similar to lowland cultivars; Khao Puang Nak, Pin Gaew 56, Ban Daeng, Plai Nghahm, and Sai Bua gave poor herbage yields.

Herbage yields from one cutting were more than 1 t/ha at 40 DT and about 2 t/ha at 60 DT, suggesting the potential production of rice herbage as animal feed.

Simple linear correlation analysis showed highly significant positive relationships between herbage yield and growth parameters (Table 2). The relationship of herbage yield with sheath and culm weight was high at 40 DT, but

very low at 60 DT. There was no relationship between plant height and herbage yield at 40 DT and a negative association at 60 DT (the sheath and culm became the dominant plant part as rice plants grew taller, especially in traditional tall cultivars).

High herbage yields can be obtained from rice varieties with vigorous growth during vegetative stage. Cultivar differences should be considered in herbage production. ■

Table 1. Herbage yield at 40 and 60 DT of 24 rice cultivars grown with irrigation. IRRI, 1989 wet season.

Rice cultivar	Herbage yield (t/ha)	
	40 DT	60 DT
<i>Deepwater rice</i>		
Ban Daeng	0.82	1.39
Huntra 60	0.88	2.00
Khao Hoi	0.74	1.59
Khao Kaset	0.84	1.53
Khao Lod Chong	1.05	1.95
Khao Mali	1.14	2.06
Khao Praguad	1.10	1.89
Khao Puang Nak	0.66	1.38
Khao Rachinee	0.93	1.88
Leb Mue Nahng 111	0.88	1.56
Luang Pratharn	1.11	1.76
Mali Tawng	0.93	1.59
Nahng Khiew	0.93	1.47
Pan Tawng	1.21	1.98
Pin Gaew 56	0.84	1.25
Plai Ngahm	0.83	1.38
RD19	0.91	1.65
Sai Bua	0.93	1.29
Sam Ruang	0.83	1.39
Tapow Gaew 161	0.88	1.83
<i>Lowland rice</i>		
B4259	1.16	1.98
Binato	1.20	-
H4	1.32	1.64
IR29723-143-3-2	0.90	1.78
LSD (0.0.5)	0.23	0.44

Table 2. Relationship between herbage yield and growth parameters of 24 rice cultivars at 40 and 60 DT.^a IRRI, 1989 wet season.

Parameter	40 DT	60 DT
Active leaves wt (t/ha)	+0.948**	+0.816**
Leaf area index	+0.714**	+0.730**
Shoot wt (t/ha)	+0.878**	+0.536**
Sheath and culm wt (t/ha)	+0.766**	+0.137ns
Dead leaves wt (t/ha)	+0.266ns	+0.247ns
Tillers (no./m ²)	+0.334ns	+0.422*
Tiller wt (g)	+0.129ns	-0.283ns
Root wt (g/m ²)	+0.016ns	+0.122ns
Height (cm)	+0.005ns	-0.450*

^a Significant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ns = nonsignificant.

Ratooning ability and potential herbage production from ratoon crops of rice cultivars

T. Kupkanchanakul, B. S. Vergara, and K. Kupkanchanakul, Agronomy, Physiology, and Agroecology Division, IRRI

A rice ratoon crop has high potential for both grain and herbage production. However, most studies on rice ratooning have emphasized grain yield.

Using the herbage from a ratoon crop to provide a continuous supply of ruminant feed after harvest of the main rice crop has received little attention.

We evaluated the ratooning ability and potential herbage production from the ratoon crops of 20 deepwater and 4 lowland rices in irrigated fields at IRRI in the 1990 dry season. Cultivars were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Main crop straw was cut 15 cm aboveground 7 d after harvest and 60 kg N/ha surface applied. The field was

irrigated to 1-5 cm water depth throughout the ratoon crop.

Of 24 cultivars studied, only 17 produced ratoons (see table). Deepwater cultivars Huntra 60, Khao Rachinee, and Luang Pratharn had very good ratooning ability, similar to that of lowland cultivars.

Plants were sampled 30 and 60 d after ratooning (DAR) and at maturity of the ratoon crop to measure biomass yield (excluding the 15-cm stubble). Deepwater rice cultivars with high ratooning ability showed high biomass yield at 30 and 60 DAR, indicating the potential of a ratoon rice crop as forage during the dry season where natural forage in rice areas is limited.

Cultivars with high ratooning ability also produced higher grain yield, suggesting the potential for grain yield from ratoon crop in areas where water is available.

Herbage and grain production from a ratoon rice crop might be another approach to increasing production, adding crop value, and increasing land use efficiency and farmer income, especially in single-crop deepwater rice areas. ■

Ratooning ability and production of ratoon crops. IRRI, 1990 dry season.

Rice cultivar	Ratoon hills (% of main crop)	Biomass yield ^a (tha)			Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
		30 DAR	60 DAR	Maturity	
<i>Lowland rice</i>					
B4259	59	1.18	4.89	7.53	2.3
Binato	56	1.41	5.44	8.45	2.9
H4	56	1.29	4.44	9.43	2.3
IR29723-143-3-2	65	1.48	4.42	8.74	2.6
<i>Deepwater rice</i>					
Ban Daeng	11	-	-	-	-
Huntra 60	72	3.30	6.75	10.28	2.3
Khao Hoi	0	-	-	-	-
Khao Kaset	23	0.80	3.50	6.14	1.6
Khao Lod Chong	20	0.85	3.40	5.35	1.1
Khao Mali	10	-	-	-	-
Khao Praguad	29	0.65	3.47	9.08	2.0
Khao Puang Nak	9	-	-	-	-
Khao Rachinee	64	3.30	8.85	9.40	2.7
Leb Mue Nahng III	0	-	-	-	-
Luang Pratharn	59	1.93	8.80	12.92	2.7
Mali Tawng	0	-	-	-	-
Nahng Khiew	13	-	-	-	-
Pan Tawng	43	1.11	4.28	9.25	2.5
Pin Gaew	0	-	-	-	-
Plai Ngahm	4	-	-	-	-
RD19	32	0.91	2.43	5.12	1.2
Saibua	0	-	-	-	-
Sam Ruang	0	-	-	-	-
Tapow Gaew 161	0	-	-	-	-
LSD (0.05)	18	1.51	2.70	ns	1.1

^a Cultivars with less than 20% ratoons were not sampled.